

SCAFET Codes

The core python codes used for AR detection and tracking can be found in `scafet.zip` folder

Description of codes

Main Figures

1. `commsenv_figures.ipynb/commsenv_figures.html`: Codes to make all the main figures.

Supplementary Figures

2. `commsenv_sfigures.ipynb/commsenv_sfigures.html`: Codes to make all supplementary figures except Fig. S18.
3. `event.ARTMIP_SCAFET.ipynb/event.ARTMIP_SCAFET.html`: Codes to make Fig. S18.

Feature Figure

1. `feature_image_commsenv.ipynb/feature_image_commsenv.html`: Codes to make the feature figure

AR Detection using SCAFET:

Detection

1. `ar_detection_pd.py`: Detection of Atmospheric Rivers (ARs) from Present Climate (PD)
2. `ar_detection_2c.py`: Detection of Atmospheric Rivers (ARs) from 2CO₂ simulations.
3. `ar_detection_4c.py`: Detection of Atmospheric Rivers (ARs) from 4CO₂ simulations.
4. `ar_detection_ERA5.py`: Detection of Atmospheric Rivers (ARs) from ERA5 reanalysis.

5. ar_detection_CMIP*.py: Detection of Atmospheric Rivers (ARs) from CMIP5 and CMIP6 simulations.

Tracking

1. arTracking.py: For tracking the detected ARs from ultra-high-resolution (UHR) simulations.
2. arTracking_ERA5.py: For tracking the detected ARs from ERA5 reanalysis data.
3. arTracking_scafet_CMIP*.py: For tracking the detected ARs from CMIP5 and CMIP6 datasets.

Data Analysis

1. figure1_cesm hires.py: Calculate annual and seasonal means for CESM UHR outputs
2. figure1_era5.py: Calculate annual and seasonal means for ERA5 outputs
3. figure1_pptn_era5.py: Calculate the ratio of AR precipitation for ERA5
4. figure1_pptn.py: Calculate the ratio of AR precipitation for CESM UHR
5. get_ppt_percentiles.py: Calculate values of precipitation quantiles
6. extreme_ppt_givenAR_ERA5.py: Calculate the probability of extreme precipitation given ARs.
7. ivtx_monthly_decom_weddy.py: Decomposition of zonal IVT
8. ivty_monthly_decom_weddy.py: Decomposition of meridional IVT
9. calc_uprime.py: Filtering U to calculate EKE
10. calc_vprime.py: Filtering V to calculate EKE

Description of Data

Sample Data

1. IVT from ERA5 reanalysis. A sample data used for the detection and tracking of ARs in Fig. S17.
2. PRECT data from ERA5 reanalysis. A sample data used for the detection and tracking of ARs in Fig. S17.
3. ivt.*.day.nc: Data for a year from PD, 2CO₂, and 4CO₂ scenarios

4. SCAFET.Tracked.AR_objs*.nc: Detected AR mask for different experiments.
5. SCAFET.Tracked.AR_props*.nc: Properties of detected ARs for different experiments.
6. xpptGivenAR*: Probability of extreme precipitation given ARs.
7. climatology_and_sigs*: Annual mean frequency and seasonal variability of ARs from different datasets and ARDTs.